

Effect of thidiazuron on the *Humulus lupulus* L. clonal micropropagation

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Abstract

The diverse effects of thidiazuron on the anatomical, morphological, and physiological characteristics of plants require careful selection of optimal regimes and dosages for clonal micropropagation tailored to each species. This article examines the impact of thidiazuron on *Humulus lupulus* L. during the shoot multiplication phase, utilizing concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 0.5 mg L⁻¹ in increments of 0.1 mg L⁻¹. The basal Murashige and Skoog medium (MSm) was supplemented with 0.1 mg L⁻¹ of 3-indoleacetic acid (IAA) and 20 g L⁻¹ of glucose. The growth and development of regenerant plants were evaluated using a novel scale based on the timing of morphological structure formation. Regenerant plants cultured on all variants of the thidiazuron-supplemented medium exhibited delayed development compared to the control group. Specifically, 62.8% of the regenerants were clusters of de novo shoots emerging from the explant nodes, while only 10.6% developed more robust shoots, characterized by small leaves and shortened internodes, indicative of chlorosis. Upon transferring these conglomerates to MSm and MSm supplemented with 0.1 mg L⁻¹ IAA, growth inhibition was observed, with development rates more than 1.5 times slower than those in the control group. Some regenerants displayed signs of overhydration and shoot deformation, resulting in non-viability. Therefore, for *Humulus lupulus* L., it is suggested that thidiazuron should be used solely for short-term stimulation of multiple de novo shoot proliferation in genotypes exhibiting low reproduction rates.

Keywords

Thidiazuron, hops (*Humulus lupulus* L.), regeneration, in vitro, morphogenesis, growth, development phases

Introduction

The regulatory mechanisms governing organogenesis and embryogenesis are primarily influenced by the balance of plant hormones, particularly auxins and cytokinins. The most commonly utilized natural auxin in cell and tissue culture is indole-3-acetic acid (IAA). In addition to natural auxins, several synthetic alternatives exist, with α -naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA) and 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) being the most prevalent. Natural cytokinins are typically N6-substituted adenine derivatives; however, synthetic cytokinins like phenylurea-type compounds are also widely used (Yamagich et al. 2010). In laboratory practices aimed at inducing plant cell regeneration, artificially synthesized growth regulators are increasingly favored due to their cost-effectiveness compared to natural analogs. Recently, there has been a surge in publications regarding thidiazuron [N-phenyl-N'-(1,2,3-thiazol-5-yl)-urea; TDZ], a multifunctional growth regulator known for initiating various physiological responses in plant cell and tissue culture (Ahmad & Shahzad 2018). Originally synthesized by Schering Corporation as a defoliant for cotton *Gossypium hirsutum* L. (Arndt et al. 1976), TDZ has since been classified as a cytokinin that elicits reactions similar to those triggered by natural cytokinins (Murphy et al. 1998). Its unique ability to function as both an auxin and cytokinin has been documented (Casanova et al. 2004). The effectiveness of thidiazuron is contingent upon several factors: concentration, exposure duration, type of cultured explant, and specific plant species. Research indicates that low concentrations of TDZ can effectively promote organogenesis through short-term exposure while higher concentrations tend to favor callus formation and somatic embryogenesis (Fengyen & Han 2002; Tulac et al. 2002). For instance, in *Echinacea purpurea* L., low TDZ concentrations have been shown to stimulate somatic embryogenesis in competent cells (Jones et al. 2007). While precise data on TDZ-induced callus types remain limited, some studies suggest that morphogenic structures capable of further regeneration can form under its influence (Jones et al. 2007; Yucesan 2018; Chung & Quyang 2021). Low TDZ concentrations (0.1–0.2 mg L⁻¹) combined with NAA have proven effective for callus formation followed by regeneration in thin cell layer cultures of *Begonia* (Nhut et al. 2005). Incorporating auxins like IAA into TDZ-containing media not only enhances callusogenesis and somatic embryogenesis efficiency but also promotes shoot regeneration (Zambre et al. 2001; Jones et al. 2007). Thidiazuron's application often leads to biochemical alterations within cells. Its presence can trigger the accumulation of peroxidase, catalase, proline, and abscisic acid (Wang et al. 1991; Tang & Newton 2005), while also increasing calcium and sodium transport within cells (Jones et al. 2007). Many enzymes influenced by TDZ

are associated with cell wall integrity and membrane fluidity (Wang et al. 1991). Additionally, TDZ's effects are linked to alterations in cytokinin biosynthesis pathways (Casanova et al. 2004; Zhang et al. 2005).

However, prolonged exposure to thidiazuron can result in morphogenetic abnormalities such as growth inhibition or shoot deformation (Liu et al. 2003). Excessive concentrations may lead to symptoms like hyperhydration and abnormal shoot morphology (Liu et al. 2003; Ahmad & Anis 2007; Shirani et al. 2010). To mitigate these negative effects, researchers recommend transitioning regenerants to media devoid of this growth regulator. Thidiazuron is regarded as one of the most effective synthetic cytokinins for plant regeneration due to its pronounced effects—up to twenty times greater than those observed with other cytokinins—complicating direct comparisons between them (Ahmad & Shahzad 2018). Despite extensive research into TDZ's action mechanisms over the years, significant gaps remain regarding its specific modes of action in regulating plant growth and morphogenesis under in vitro conditions. This study aims to elucidate the effects of thidiazuron on clonal micropropagation in *Humulus lupulus*.

Materials and methods

The object was a sterile culture of the genotype of common hop collected in Altai Krai, which according to morphometric characteristics was classified as a promising form for participation in the breeding process. At the stage of shoot multiplication, basic medium with mineral composition according to Murashige and Skoog (MSm) prescription supplemented with 0.1 mg of L⁻¹ 3-indolylacetic acid (IAA) and glucose (20 g of L⁻¹) was used. Additionally, thidiazuron was added to the medium at a concentration of 0.1-0.5 mg L⁻¹, in increments of 0.1 mg L⁻¹. Hormone-free MSm medium served as a control. All works were carried out according to the generally accepted methods of cell and tissue culture in vitro. The culture was carried out on racks under standard conditions at 21-23 °C, 16 hours of light on a day of illumination of 3000-5000 lux. Glass tubes of 21×200 mm size were used as culture vessels. The sample volume for each variant was 15 specimens. The growth and development of regenerants were evaluated according to our original scale. In the cultivation process, the stages of growth were observed: germination and intensive growth. The dates of morphological structures formation at the stage of intensive growth were fixed: formation of 2 pairs of true leaves (I phase), 3-4 (II), 5-6 (III) and more than 7 pairs of true leaves (IV). The onset of the phase was recorded when 75-80% of the regenerants entered it. In addition, the number and length of the shoots, the presence and size of the callus, the development of the root system, the visually distinguishable deformations and abnormalities were observed.

Results and discussion

The growth and development of hop explants in in vitro culture differed depending on the composition of the nutrient medium and the varietal characteristics. The first morphogenetic response of hop plants when grown in artificial nutrient media was the formation of the root system. Therefore, the rhizogenesis process was observed in single explants already on the fifth day. After 10–12 days of cultivation in control MSm medium and medium MSm+0.1 mg L⁻¹ of PPI, which did not contain thidiazuron, root development was observed in 75% of cases.

At the initial stages, the development of the root system differed slightly depending on the composition of the nutrient medium. In plants grown on the control variant of nutrient medium, roots in the amount of 1–3 per explant did not exceed 2.0 cm in length, were thin and practically did not branch. In the nutrient medium with the addition of UIC, the number of roots increased to 2–4, root hairs formed on them, but the maximum length of the roots did not exceed 0.5 cm. In medium containing thidiazuron at a concentration of 0.1–0.5 mg L⁻¹, only aerial roots were formed in single specimens. Most of the explants formed callus in the basal part of the stem placed in nutrient medium during the first two weeks of cultivation. The maximum size of callus tissue, 0.5–0.7 cm, was observed in the variant with the addition of TDZ at a concentration of 0.1 mg L⁻¹. In medium containing 0.4–0.5 mg of L⁻¹ thidiazuron, axillary buds developed in the thickness of the medium or directly above its surface, often formed strong shoots of larger diameter, reddish color, without signs of vitrification. In the initial stage of development, the exogenous influence of auxin promoted the accelerated growth and development of hop shoots. The formation of 2 pairs of leaves in the media containing Auxin occurred on day 13, whereas in the control variant containing no hormones, the regenerants entered the I phase of development on day (Table 1). In all nutrient media, shoots formed quite friendly, the maximum height of the regenerants on the control was 3.2 cm and with the addition of HA 4.1 cm.

Table 1. Formation of morphological structures during intensive in vitro growth of *Humulus lupulus* L., days

Nutrient media composition	Growth stages			
	I	II	III	IV
MSm (control)	16	23	26	40
MSm+0.1 mg L ⁻¹ UIC	13	20	26	36
MSm+0.1 mg L ⁻¹ UIC	20	30	-	-
MSm+0.1 mg L ⁻¹ UIC+0.2 mg L ⁻¹ TDZ	20	-	-	-
MSm+0.1 mg L ⁻¹ UIC+0.3 mg L ⁻¹ TDZ	20	-	-	-
MSm+0.1 mg L ⁻¹ UIC+0.4 mg L ⁻¹ TDZ	20	-	-	-
MSm+0.1 mg L ⁻¹ UIC+0.5 mg L ⁻¹ TDZ	23	-	-	-

According to Liu et al. (2003) the presence of thidiazuron in the medium can contribute to the decrease in the rate of growth and development of plants. This fact is confirmed by the data obtained in our experiment. The shoots formed in the medium with the addition of TDZ reached the I stage only 20–23 days, although in some samples the development of two pairs of leaves was observed after 13–14 days of cultivation. In regenerants cultivated in all media variants with the addition of thidiazuron (0.1–0.5 mg L⁻¹), the shoots had only 1 pair of leaves or only viable buds in the first stage of development, which were larger than in the control. On media without thidiazuron, plants showed larger leaves. During three weeks of cultivation in control and auxin-enriched (AUC) media, the rate of plant growth and development equalized, and after 26 days, the regenerants entered stage III of development. Regenerants formed in media with thidiazuron lagged behind in their development – after three weeks of cultivation, only three samples reached the II stage of development, i.e., formed 3–4 pairs of leaves, the rest of the plants remained in the first stage of development.

Regenerating agents had small leaves, shortened internodes, and the apex of the shoot almost always had signs of chlorosis. Most regenerants (62.8%) were de novo shoot bundles located at the nodes of the explants. More than a quarter of the planted specimens (26.6%) formed only callus without shoot development. Hop regenerants cultivated in auxin-enriched medium entered the last IV stage of development fastest on 36 days. The plants in the control group formed seven and more internodes somewhat later, on the 40th day. Below, we present the average height of shoots (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Root length of *Humulus lupulus* L. regenerants entering Phase IV of the morphological structures.

The external habitus of the regenerants in the medium with UIC did not differ from the control, except for a more developed root system. The other regenerants remained in stage I of morphological structure formation or did not reach it at all, and shoots with signs of vitrification were also observed. Prolonged passage - more

than 20 days, in TDZ media - significantly reduced the ability of the shoots to further grow and develop further, and the number of anomalies increased. After three weeks of cultivation, some conglomerates formed in TDZ-containing medium were transferred to MSm and MSm+0.1 mg L⁻¹ UIC for elongation.

The plants were more than 1.5 times slower in growth and development compared to regenerants without the preceding passage in TDZ medium. After 45 days, the reproduction rate was calculated, which was 2–3 regenerants per explant in the samples with thidiazuron in the preceding passage, while in the control – up to 5 pcs/explant. At the same time, some regenerants with signs of hyperhydration and shoot deformation were not viable.

Conclusion

Thus, the use of thidiazuron for common hop is possible only for short-term stimulation of multiple proliferation of shoots de novo for genotypes with a low reproduction rate with subsequent transfer of the formed shoots to a hormone-free medium for elongation, considering the varietal-specific reaction. When conglomerates were transferred from TDZ medium to MSm and MSm+0.1 mg L⁻¹ PPI, the growth and development of regenerants was more than 1.5 times slower than in control samples not exposed to TDZ. Prolonged exposure to thidiazuron (more than 20 days) leads to the formation of de novo shoot conglomerates in hops with nonviable shoots or with single depressed short shoots with small leaves, shortened internodes, signs of chlorosis, hyperhydration and shoot deformation.

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